

CHALLENGES IN TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING AND TLE PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 10 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the relationship between the challenges in technology and livelihood education modular distance learning and the TLE performance of Grade 10 students. The researcher utilized the descriptive-survey and descriptive-correlational methods of research in conducting the study. The researcher conducted the study in Dr. Panfilo Castro National High School. Through the use of stratified random sampling technique, forty percent of the total population (139) of Grade 10 students are identified as the respondents in this study. The first part of the study is about the profile of the respondents. The study revealed the following data: majority of the respondents were 16 years year old and female dominates the male respondents. Most of the respondents belong to the low family income category and both the fathers and mothers of the respondents were mostly high school graduates. The majority of the respondents' fathers were working full-time while few were unemployed while in terms of mother's occupation, most of the respondents' mothers were unemployed while few were working part-time. Most of the respondents have smartphone/Android/IOS cellphone while few have desktop computer, and the majority of the respondents were at Good proficient level in terms of their performance. The second part of the study is only limited to the five (5) modular distance learning challenges, namely, technological challenges, individual challenges, domestic challenges, institutional challenges, and community challenges. On the other hand, the TLE performance will only cover the 1st and 2nd quarter grade the respondents in TLE subject. The challenges were measured using a questionnaire with twenty-five (25) statements. The students' averages of ratings in TLE for the 1st and 2nd quarters and weighted means have been correlated. Based on the analysis of the gathered data, this study found out that there is no significant relationship between the challenges in technology and livelihood education modular distance learning and the TLE performance of Grade 10 students. It means that the students' TLE performance was not dictated by the challenges in modular distance learning or vice versa.

Keywords: modular distance learning, learning challenges, TLE performance